

Polynomial Approximations in the Polytope Model: Bringing the Power of Quasi-Polynomials to the Masses

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Abstract

This paper addresses one issue in the polyhedral model of loop nests that limits its practical applicability. We present methods for avoiding the use of quasi-polynomials when enumerating integer points in polyhedra, by computing polynomial approximations of the quasi-polynomials and also polynomial upper and lower bounds of the quasi-polynomial. We propose two methods and different variants thereof. An evaluation on a set of systems of linear equalities generated by several compiler analyses shows that the accuracy of our more advanced method is similar to or better than the accuracy of existing techniques, while the computation is faster on difficult problems.

1. Introduction and Motivation

A certain class of nested for-loops in embedded systems applications can be modeled with polyhedra. Specifically, if inner loop counters are bounded by affine functions of outer loop counters and loop-invariant expressions whose values are unknown at analysis time, then these bounds define a set bounded by affine inequalities (a polyhedron) in the vector space of the loop indices and the loop-invariant expressions, which are treated as symbolic constants or *parameters*. The loop nest is then represented by the integer points in this polytope, where both loop counters and parameters are assumed to take on integer values only.

In this *polyhedral model*, many interesting properties, such as the computational load of the loop nests [23], their power consumption, execution time, e.g., [26, 27], amount of parallelism, e.g., [11, 15], and memory behavior, e.g., [12, 14, 32] can be derived from the number of integer points in these polyhedra or in their image by various affine functions. These metrics are then used to drive optimizations and parallelization of the compiled program. More examples, also in other fields of application, are given in [19, 30, 32].

The number of integer points in a parametric polyhedron, called its *enumerator*, can be written as a closed-form function of the parameters, called *quasi-polynomial* as it

```
for (i = 0; i <= n/2; ++i)
  for (j = i; j <= (m+2)/3; ++j)
    S1;
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Figure 1. A simple loop nest example

resembles a polynomial. Unfortunately, the use of quasi-polynomials in production tool-chains is hindered by their complex and potentially big-sized data structure, which makes them hard to manipulate. Some analysis techniques, such as the use of Bernstein expansion to compute bounds on memory requirements [6], require these enumerators to be (approximated by) polynomials. In most applications (here, all the above examples except [14]), the precision of quasi-polynomial could advantageously be traded for a better ease of manipulation and smaller size. Indeed, most of the applications mentioned here would just need an approximate number of integer points in a polyhedron to work. In many cases, the enumerator must be ensured to be less than or greater than some constant, which in turn raises the need for safe polynomial upper and lower bounds on the considered number of points.

The next section illustrates the complexity problem on a simple but concrete example. Section 3 presents the formal background and results that we will use throughout this paper. Existing approaches are presented in Section 4. Two different approximation and bounding methods are then presented, a simple method directly modifying the polyhedron's enumerator is shown in Section 5, while the other, more complicated method is explained in more detail in Sections 6, 7 and 8. Both methods are then experimentally evaluated and compared against each other, other approximations and the exact enumerator in Section 9. Finally, the main results of this article and ongoing research directions are given in Sections 10 and 11.

2. Illustrative Example

Consider the code fragment in Figure 1 and assume we want to know how many times S1 is executed for different values of n and m . Using standard techniques to extract affine

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constraints from code, available in several modern industrial and research compilers, e.g., [1, 20, 25], this problem is equivalent to finding the number of elements in the set

$$D = \{(i, j) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 \mid 0 \leq i \leq j \wedge 2i \leq n \wedge 3j \leq m+2\} \quad (1)$$

and the solution is $\#D =$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left\lfloor \frac{m+2}{3} \right\rfloor^2 + \frac{3}{2} \left\lfloor \frac{m+2}{3} \right\rfloor + 1 & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ \frac{1}{8}m^2 - \frac{1}{2} \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor n - \frac{1}{8}n + \left\lfloor \frac{m+2}{3} \right\rfloor \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor \\ \quad + \frac{3}{4} \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor + \left\lfloor \frac{m+2}{3} \right\rfloor + 1 & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ is the greatest integer part (floor) of x and

$$C_1 = \{(m, n) \mid m \geq -2 \wedge 2m \leq 3n - 4\}$$

$$C_2 = \{(m, n) \mid n \geq 0 \wedge 3n \leq 2m + 3\}.$$

A different representation of the same function is

$$\begin{cases} \frac{m^2}{18} + \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{13}{18}, \frac{11}{18} \right]_m m + \left[1, \frac{20}{9}, \frac{14}{9} \right]_m & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ -\frac{1}{8}n^2 + \frac{mn}{6} + \left[\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{6} \right]_n m \\ \quad + \left[\left[\frac{1}{4}, \frac{7}{12}, \frac{5}{12} \right]_m, \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{6}, \frac{2}{3} \right]_m \right]_n n \\ \quad + \left[\left[1, \frac{5}{3}, \frac{4}{3} \right]_m, \left[\frac{5}{8}, \frac{23}{24}, \frac{19}{24} \right]_m \right]_n & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where a bracketed list of s elements with subscript p evaluates to the element with index $p \bmod s$. For example,

$$\frac{m^2}{18} + \left[\frac{1}{2}, \frac{13}{18}, \frac{11}{18} \right]_m m + \left[1, \frac{20}{9}, \frac{14}{9} \right]_m$$

is equivalent to

$$\begin{cases} \frac{m^2}{18} + \frac{1}{2}m + 1 & \text{if } m \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \\ \frac{m^2}{18} + \frac{13}{18}m + \frac{20}{9} & \text{if } m \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ \frac{m^2}{18} + \frac{11}{18}m + \frac{14}{9} & \text{if } m \equiv 2 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

The number of elements that may appear in a list in a formula of type (3) is directly proportional to the coefficients that appear in the constraints that describe the set D (1) and is therefore exponential in the input size (i.e., the number of bits needed to express the problem). The size of formulas of type (2) is polynomial in the input size (if the number of variables is fixed), but may still be quite large. Furthermore, these formulas contain $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ -expressions, which makes them more difficult to manipulate than standard polynomials. If we are only interested in the *approximate* number of elements in D , then we can instead compute the approximate (piecewise) polynomial

$$\#D \approx \begin{cases} \frac{m^2}{18} + \frac{11}{18}m + \frac{14}{9} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ -\frac{n^2}{8} + \frac{mn}{6} + \frac{13}{24}n + \frac{m}{4} + \frac{17}{16} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

which is accurate to about 5% over values of m and n between -100 and 100 and avoids the disadvantages of both types of exact formulas.

3. Background Theory

A unimodular matrix is a square ($d \times d$) integer matrix with determinant ± 1 , which therefore defines a bijection from \mathbb{Z}^d to \mathbb{Z}^d . A d -dimensional (rational) polyhedron is a subset of \mathbb{Q}^d bounded by linear inequalities with integer coefficients. A bounded polyhedron is called a polytope and the extremal points of a polytope are called its vertices. In a *parametric* polyhedron $P_{\mathbf{p}}$, the ‘‘constants’’ in the linear inequalities may be affine combinations of a set of n integer parameters \mathbf{p} , i.e.,

$$P_{\mathbf{p}} = \{ \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{Q}^d \mid A\mathbf{x} + B\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{c} \geq \mathbf{0} \}, \quad (5)$$

for some $A \in \mathbb{Z}^{m \times d}$, $B \in \mathbb{Z}^{m \times n}$ and $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{Z}^m$. A parametric polytope is a parametric polyhedron that is bounded for each value of the parameters. We are interested in the (approximate) number of integer points in parametric polytopes, as in (1). The number of integer points in a parametric polytope $P_{\mathbf{p}}$ will be denoted $\#(P_{\mathbf{p}} \cap \mathbb{Z}^d)$, or sometimes $\#P_{\mathbf{p}}$ for brevity. Without loss of generality [32], we will assume in this paper that all parametric polytopes are full-dimensional. Note that any procedure for solving this problem can be extended to the more general problem of finding the (approximate) number of elements in the projection of the integer points in a parametric polytope [30].

The exact number of integer points in a parametric polytope, i.e., the *enumerator* of the parametric polytope, is a piecewise *quasi-polynomial* in the parameters. A quasi-polynomial is a polynomial expression with coefficients that depend periodically on the parameters \mathbf{p} . These *periodic numbers* $u(\mathbf{p})$ can be represented by an explicit table of coefficients as in (3) or implicitly as fractional parts $\{x\} = x - \lfloor x \rfloor$ or floors as in (2). The *period* of a periodic number is the (componentwise) smallest s such that $u(\mathbf{p}) = u(\mathbf{p}')$ whenever $\mathbf{p} \equiv \mathbf{p}' \pmod{s}$. The period of a quasi-polynomial is the least common multiple of the periods of its periodic coefficients. For example, the periods of the quasi-polynomials in (3) (and also in (2)), are $(3, 1)$ and $(3, 2)$.

The piecewise quasi-polynomials can be computed in at least two ways. The first method, pioneered by Clauss [7], is based on interpolation and produces a result of the form (3). The second method is based on Barvinok’s algorithm [2, 32] and produces a result of the form (2). We will concentrate on this second method, since it produces polynomially-sized output. Both methods start by computing the (parametric) vertices of the parametric polytope [16]. These may be different in different *chambers*, i.e., polyhedra in the parameter space forming a partition of the polytope’s definition domain. For example, for the underlying polytope P of D (1), i.e., $D = P \cap \mathbb{Z}^2$, the vertices are

$$\begin{cases} \left\{ \left(\frac{m+2}{3}, \frac{m+2}{3} \right), \left(0, \frac{m+2}{3} \right), (0, 0) \right\} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ \left\{ \left(0, \frac{m+2}{3} \right), (0, 0), \left(\frac{n}{2}, \frac{m+2}{3} \right), \left(\frac{n}{2}, \frac{n}{2} \right) \right\} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Each of these vertices is obtained by taking a subset $S \subset \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ of d linearly independent inequalities from (5) and solving

$$A_S \mathbf{x} + B_S \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{c}_S = \mathbf{0}.$$

Each coordinate of a vertex is therefore a rational affine expression in the parameters. For example, the vertex $(\frac{n}{2}, \frac{n}{2})$ is obtained by solving $i = j$ and $2i = n$. For further details on how Barvinok's algorithm is then applied, we refer to [32]. We only note here that each resulting quasi-polynomial is a polynomial expression in the floors of integer linear combinations of vertex coordinates.

A sufficient condition for the enumerator of P to have period $\mathbf{1}$, i.e., to be a (non-periodic) polynomial, is for all vertices of P to be integer for all (integer) values of the parameters [7]. This can easily be explained from the general structure of the output of Barvinok's algorithm. If the vertices are integer for all values of the parameters, then each vertex coordinate is an *integer* affine combination of the parameters and the floors may be omitted, resulting in a polynomial. The same reasoning shows that the periodicity of $\#P$ is independent of the constants in the affine expressions of the vertex coordinates, which means that it is independent of the vector \mathbf{c} in (5). We therefore have the following theorem.

THEOREM 1 (Non-periodicity condition). *If, for each vertex $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{p}) = M\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q}$ of P defined by a set of d equalities $A_S \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{p}) + B_S \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{c}_S = \mathbf{0}$, we have*

$$M = A_S^{-1} B_S \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times n} \quad (7)$$

then the enumerator of P is a piecewise (non-periodic) polynomial.

Note that Theorem 1 specifies a sufficient, but not necessary condition [17].

4. Related Work

Many researchers have considered the problem of computing the exact number of integer points in parametric polytopes and related problems. We refer to [30–32] for an overview. Here we will only discuss some approximation methods.

Several authors [21, 23, 26, 27] express the number of integer points in a polyhedron as nested sums which are then decomposed using Bernoulli formulae or Newton series. If any coefficient is not ± 1 , then the result may be approximate, even if the exact enumerator is a (non-periodic) polynomial. In some cases, this approximation can be shown to be an over-approximation [27]. Furthermore, the polyhedron needs to be split so that it can be expressed as a union of nested intervals, possibly leading to many more pieces than the chambers in the exact enumerator. On the other hand, the work of [27] is in some sense more general than ours, because it allows for polynomial upper bounds in the sums (rather than affine expressions). The extension of [21]

to counting the number of solutions to Presburger formulas is covered by applying the techniques of [30]. Note that Pugh [21] also proposes an exact approach in the presence of rational bounds, but this approach is worst-case exponential.

Heine and Slowik [11] propose to replace each periodic coefficient by its average value. This requires an explicit enumeration of all the different values of the periodic coefficients and is therefore worst-case exponential (in the input size), even for fixed dimensions.

Rabl [22] computes the volume of a parametric polytope and even allows the polytopes to be non-linearly parameterized. He uses an inefficient triangulation, however [19]. In our experiments in Section 9, we will use a more efficient triangulation. As we will see in Section 6, our approximations also enjoy a better worst-case bound on the approximation error. Our basic lower and upper bound technique of Section 8 also applies to volume computations.

Devos et al. [8, 9] compute bounds on the values attained by a quasi-polynomial over the integer points in a polytope. They compare several methods for obtaining such bounds, including one based on first computing a polynomial approximation of the quasi-polynomial using the techniques presented in this paper.

5. (Safely) Approximating Quasi-polynomials

The simplest way of transforming a piecewise quasi-polynomial into a piecewise polynomial is to first rewrite each floor $\lfloor \langle \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + g \rfloor$, with $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{Q}^n$ and $g \in \mathbb{Q}$, as $\langle \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + g - \{\langle \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + g\}$ and then to replace each of the fractional parts by a constant. In particular, if we are only interested in an approximation and not in a lower or upper bound, we simply replace each fractional part $\{(\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c)/m\}$, where $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{Z}^n$ and $c, m \in \mathbb{Z}$ by the average of all possible values attained by this fractional part, i.e., $\frac{m-1}{2m}$. This is a variation of the technique of Heine and Slowik [11], except that they take the average of exponentially many coefficients, while we simply manipulate a polynomially-sized representation of quasi-polynomials.

EXAMPLE 1. *Rewriting the first quasi-polynomial in (2), results in*

$$\frac{m^2}{18} - \frac{1}{3} \left\{ \frac{m+2}{3} \right\} m + \frac{13}{18} m + \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{m+2}{3} \right\}^2 - \frac{13}{6} \left\{ \frac{m+2}{3} \right\} + \frac{20}{9}.$$

Replacing each fractional part in this expression by $\frac{2}{6} = \frac{1}{3}$, produces the first polynomial in (4).

Since each quasi-polynomial produced by Barvinok's algorithm is a polynomial expression in floors of affine expressions, the fractional parts never appear as coefficients of the terms of highest degree. Replacing them by a constant therefore does not disturb the coefficients of the highest degree terms.

To obtain a lower or an upper bound, we replace each $\{(\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c)/m\}$ that appears in the coefficient of a monomial by either 0 or $\frac{m-1}{m}$, depending on the sign of the mono-

mial. Note that, in general, this requires that we know the sign of each individual parameter. If the sign of a parameter varies in a chamber, it therefore has to be split in two.

6. Approximating Parametric Polytopes

Instead of first computing the enumerator of P and then approximating the resulting piecewise quasi-polynomial by a piecewise polynomial, we can also approximate P by another parametric polytope P' which is guaranteed, by Theorem 1, to have a piecewise polynomial as enumerator. In particular, we will apply an integer linear transformation L to P such that $P' = LP$ satisfies the condition of Theorem 1. Assuming for a moment that we can find such a transformation, it is clear that L is not unimodular since otherwise P would also satisfy the condition of Theorem 1. Each unit cell $C = \{\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{x} \mid \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{Z}^d \wedge \mathbf{0} \leq \mathbf{x} < \mathbf{1}\}$, which contains a single integer point \mathbf{v} , is therefore expanded into the cell LC , which contains $\det(L)$ integer points. So the change of variables $\mathbf{x}' = L\mathbf{x}$ multiplies the number of integer points by roughly $\det(L)$. Hence we have:

$$\#(P_{\mathbf{p}} \cap \mathbb{Z}^d) \approx \frac{\#(P'_{\mathbf{p}} \cap \mathbb{Z}^d)}{\det(L)}. \quad (8)$$

For example, multiplying the underlying polytope P of $D(1)$ by $L = \begin{bmatrix} 6 & 0 \\ 0 & 6 \end{bmatrix}$, we obtain

$$\#LP = \begin{cases} 2m^2 + 11m + 15 & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ -\frac{9}{2}n^2 + 6mn + \frac{27}{2}n + 2m + 5 & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2. \end{cases}$$

Since $\det(L) = 36$, we have as an approximation

$$\#D \approx \begin{cases} \frac{m^2}{18} + \frac{11}{36}m + \frac{5}{12} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_1 \\ -\frac{n^2}{8} + \frac{mn}{6} + \frac{3}{8}n + \frac{m}{18} + \frac{5}{36} & \text{if } (m, n) \in C_2. \end{cases}$$

The expansion $P' = LP$ only roughly multiplies the number of points by $\det(L)$ because the parametric polytope P is not generally made of an integer number of unit cells. Indeed, the approximation error comes from the integer points $\mathbf{x}' \in LC$ of expanded unit cells such that either the offset of C is not in P while \mathbf{x}' is in P' , i.e., $\mathbf{x}' \in LP \cap \mathbb{Z}^d$ but $C \cap P \cap \mathbb{Z}^d = \emptyset$ (\mathbf{x}' is an *extra point*), or the offset of C is in P while \mathbf{x}' is not in P' , i.e., $\mathbf{x}' \notin LP \cap \mathbb{Z}^d$ but $C \cap P \cap \mathbb{Z}^d \neq \emptyset$ (\mathbf{x}' is a *missing point*). The presence of missing points tends to under-approximate $\#P$, while extra points tend to over-approximate $\#P$. It can be shown (see [18, Section 4.6.3]) that the approximation error is bounded by $(g-1)/g$ times the number of integer points in the facets (the ‘‘boundary’’) of P with $g = \det(L)$. To obtain the closest possible approximation, we should therefore prefer linear transformations with small determinant. Note that the contribution of each unit cell corresponds to the relative proportion of rational points mapping to integer points through L that belong to P . As $g = \det(L)$ tends to infinity, so do the denominators of the considered rational points, and the approximation (8) tends to the *volume* of P .

7. Computing the Expansion Matrix

We will now consider how to compute an integer linear transformation L such that LP satisfies the condition of Theorem 1. We will first explain how to compute a suitable transformation for a single vertex and then show how to combine the transformations for all vertices into a single linear transformation.

7.1 The Expansion Matrix for a Single Vertex

The simplest way of ensuring LP satisfies condition (7) of Theorem 1 for a particular transformed vertex $L\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{p}) = LM\mathbf{p} + L\mathbf{q}$, i.e.,

$$LM \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times n},$$

is to scale the coordinates of $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{p}) = M\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{q}$ individually. That is, let m_i be the least common multiple of the elements in row i of M and let L be the diagonal matrix with the m_i on the diagonal, then $LM \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times n}$.

EXAMPLE 2. Consider the following parametric polytope,

$$P_{(s,t)} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2i - 3j + 2s - 4t - 1 \geq 0 \quad (a) \\ (i, j) \mid \quad -i + 4j + 6t - 3 \geq 0 \quad (b) \\ \quad \quad \quad -i + 6s + 4t + 12 \geq 0 \quad (c) \end{array} \right\} \quad (9)$$

and consider the vertex defined by saturating constraints (a) and (b), i.e.,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & -3 \\ -1 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_1(s, t) + \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -4 \\ 0 & 6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} s \\ t \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ -3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

We have $\mathbf{v}_1 = (-\frac{8}{5}s - \frac{2}{5}t + \frac{13}{5}, -\frac{2}{5}s - \frac{8}{5}t + \frac{7}{5})$ and therefore $L_{\mathbf{v}_1} = \text{diag}(5, 5)$. We similarly find $\mathbf{v}_2 = (6s + 4t + 12, \frac{3}{2}s - \frac{t}{2} + \frac{15}{4})$ and $L_{\mathbf{v}_2} = \text{diag}(1, 2)$ (note that we only consider the coefficients of the parameters to determine $L_{\mathbf{v}_2}$), and $\mathbf{v}_3 = (6s + 4t + 12, \frac{14}{3}s + \frac{4}{3}t + \frac{23}{3})$ and $L_{\mathbf{v}_3} = \text{diag}(1, 3)$.

The diagonal linear transformation computed above is an *orthogonal* expansion, i.e., it expands the polytope along the canonical basis vectors. Of all suitable linear transformations, it is, however, in general not the one with the smallest determinant. To compute a linear transformation with the smallest determinant, we need to take a closer look at condition (7) of Theorem 1. The objective is to find a linear integer transformation L such that for $L\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{p}) = LA_S^{-1}B_S\mathbf{p} + L\mathbf{q}$ we have

$$LA_S^{-1}B_S \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times n} \quad \text{or} \quad M' = (A_S L^{-1})^{-1} B_S \in \mathbb{Z}^{d \times n}.$$

In particular, each of the columns of M' needs to belong to \mathbb{Z}^d , which means that each of the columns of B_S needs to be an element of the lattice $(A_S L^{-1})\mathbb{Z}^d$, i.e., the set of all elements that can be written as an integer linear combination of the columns of the non-singular matrix $A_S L^{-1}$. In other words, we need to find an integer linear matrix L such that the lattice $B_S \mathbb{Z}^n$ is a sub-lattice of $H\mathbb{Z}^d$, i.e., $B_S \mathbb{Z}^n \subset H\mathbb{Z}^d$, with $H = A_S L^{-1}$. Since $HL = A_S$, we see that $A_S \mathbb{Z}^d$ is

also a sub-lattice of $H\mathbb{Z}^d$. A $d \times d$ integer matrix H that spans such a lattice can be computed by taking the left Hermite normal form [24] of the matrix obtained by concatenating the column-vectors of A_S and B_S :

$$[A_S \ B_S] = [H \ 0]U = [H \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} U_{1,1} & U_{1,2} \\ U_{2,1} & U_{2,2} \end{bmatrix},$$

where U is unimodular (and H is lower-triangular), i.e., $A_S = HU_{1,1}$. Any other lattice $E\mathbb{Z}^d$ containing both $A_S\mathbb{Z}^d$ and $B_S\mathbb{Z}^n$ also contains $H\mathbb{Z}^d$, i.e., $H\mathbb{Z}^d \subset E\mathbb{Z}^d$. This means that $H = EK$, with K some non-singular integer matrix, i.e., $|\det(K)| \geq 1$, and so $|\det(E)| \leq |\det(H)|$. $L = U_{1,1}$ will therefore have the smallest determinant of all suitable integer linear transformation matrices.

EXAMPLE 3. Consider once more the parametric polytope defined in (9) and its vertex \mathbf{v}_1 (10). The Hermite normal form of $[A_S \ B_S]$ is

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2-3 & 2-4 \\ -1 & 4 & 0 & 6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2-3 & 2-4 \\ -1 & 4 & 0 & 6 \\ 1-2 & 1-2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

We therefore find

$$L_{\mathbf{v}_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -3 \\ -1 & 4 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Note that $\det(L_{\mathbf{v}_1}) = 5$, while using the orthogonal expansion we found a linear transformation with determinant 25. For the other vertices, we similarly find

$$L_{\mathbf{v}_2} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 4 \\ 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad L_{\mathbf{v}_3} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -3 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

7.2 A Common Expansion Matrix for all Vertices

In the previous subsection we showed how to compute an expansion matrix such that the non-periodicity condition (7) holds for a particular vertex of the expanded parametric polytope. For Theorem 1 to apply, however, *all* vertices need to satisfy the non-periodicity condition (7). We therefore need to combine the expansion matrices L_k of the individual vertices \mathbf{v}_k into a single expansion matrix L . It is clear that any further integer linear expansion L'_k of $L_k P$ will preserve the non-periodicity condition for vertex \mathbf{v}_k . We are therefore looking for an integer linear expansion matrix L of minimal determinant such that $L = L'_k L_k$ for all k and for some integer linear transformation matrices L'_k . Equivalently, $L^{-1}L'_k = L_k^{-1}$ and so each of the lattices $L_k^{-1}\mathbb{Z}^d$ is a sub-lattice of $L^{-1}\mathbb{Z}^d$.

We already know how to compute such an L^{-1} from the previous subsection. In particular, we compute the left Hermite normal form of the matrix made up of all the column-vectors of $L_1^{-1}, \dots, L_q^{-1}$:

$$[L_1^{-1} \ L_2^{-1} \ \dots \ L_q^{-1}] = [\Lambda \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]U.$$

¹Hermite normal forms can be extended to rational matrices by putting them to a common denominator

We have

$$L_k^{-1} = \Lambda U_{1,k} \quad \text{or} \quad \Lambda^{-1} = U_{1,k}^{-1} L_k,$$

for each vertex \mathbf{v}_k . The common expansion matrix is therefore $L = \Lambda^{-1}$ (and $L'_k = U_{1,k}^{-1}$). As before, Λ is of maximal determinant and so L is of minimal determinant. Note that in the case of orthogonal expansions, i.e., all the L_k are diagonal, this process simplifies to computing a diagonal matrix L with as entries the least common multiples of the corresponding entries in the L_k .

EXAMPLE 4. The common expansion matrix for the orthogonal expansion matrices computed in Example 2 is $L = \text{diag}(\text{lcm}\{5, 1, 1\}, \text{lcm}\{5, 2, 3\}) = \text{diag}(5, 30)$, i.e., $i' = 5i$ and $j' = 30j$. The corresponding expanded parametric polytope is therefore

$$P'_{(s,t)} = \left\{ (i, j) \mid \begin{array}{l} 4i' - 1j' + 20s - 40t - 10 \geq 0 \\ -3i' + 2j' + 90t - 45 \geq 0 \\ -i' + 30s + 20t + 60 \geq 0 \end{array} \right\}$$

and we find

$$\begin{aligned} \#P_{(s,t)} &\approx \frac{\#(P'_{(s,t)} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2)}{150} \\ &\approx \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{4541}{150}s + \frac{2629}{150}t + \frac{476}{25}, \end{aligned}$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$. This approximation has an average relative approximation error of 1.7% over values of s and t between -100 and 100 .

EXAMPLE 5. For the expansion matrices computed in Example 3, we find

$$\begin{aligned} [L_{\mathbf{v}_1}^{-1} \ L_{\mathbf{v}_2}^{-1} \ L_{\mathbf{v}_3}^{-1}] &= \frac{1}{30} \begin{bmatrix} 24 & 18 & 0 & -30 & -30 & -60 \\ 6 & 12 & -10 & -20 & 0 & -15 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \frac{1}{30} \begin{bmatrix} 6 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 4 & 5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} U \end{aligned}$$

and so the common expansion matrix is

$$L = \Lambda^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 0 \\ -4 & 6 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Note that $\det(L) = 30$, which is less than the determinant of 150 of the orthogonal expansion matrix computed in Example 4. Applying the transformation $i' = 5i$, $j' = -4i + 6j$ (or $i = i'/5$, $j = 2i'/15 + j'/6$), we obtain the expanded parametric polytope

$$P''_{(s,t)} = \left\{ (i, j) \mid \begin{array}{l} -j' + 4s - 8t - 2 \geq 0 \quad (a') \\ i' + 2j' + 18t - 9 \geq 0 \quad (b') \\ -i' + 30s + 20t + 60 \geq 0 \quad (c') \end{array} \right\} \quad (11)$$

and we find

$$\begin{aligned} \#P_{(s,t)} &\approx \frac{\#(P''_{(s,t)} \cap \mathbb{Z}^2)}{30} \\ &\approx \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{931}{30}s + \frac{539}{30}t + 20, \end{aligned}$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$. This approximation has an average relative approximation error of 1.3% over values of s and t between -100 and 100 .

If there is more than one chamber in the enumerator of a parametric polytope P , then we may choose to either compute a common expansion matrix for all vertices that appear in any of the chambers, or to compute a common expansion matrix for each chamber separately, only taking into account the vertices that are active on this chamber. Because the number of vertices active on a given chamber is smaller than the total number of vertices, the determinant of the expansion matrix specific to a given chamber may be smaller than the determinant of the global expansion matrix. The approximation may therefore be more accurate. This increase in accuracy comes with a certain cost, however, not only in the computation of the expansion matrices themselves, but also in a loss of opportunity for optimizing some computations across different chambers [28].

8. Computing Safe Bounds using Inflation/Deflation

As explained in Section 6, the expanded polytope may have extra integer points that do not correspond to any integer point in the original polytope and it may also be missing some integer points that *do* correspond to an integer point in the original polytope. To obtain an upper bound, we need to *inflate* the original or expanded polytope slightly to ensure that the inflated and expanded polytope contains all missing points. Similarly, to obtain a lower bound, we need to *deflate* the original or expanded polytope to ensure that the deflated and expanded polytope does not contain any extra points.

More precisely, a missing point is an integer point $L\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{q}'$ in the expanded space that is the image under L of a rational point $\mathbf{x} + L^{-1}\mathbf{q}'$ in the unit cell $\mathbf{x} + [0, 1]^d$ at some integer point $\mathbf{x} \in P \cap \mathbb{Z}^d$. To ensure that all these points are included, we need to impose

$$L((P \cap \mathbb{Z}^d) + ([0, 1]^d \cap L^{-1}\mathbb{Z}^d)) \subset L'P, \quad (12)$$

where L' is a combination of expansion and inflation. The inflation can be obtained by relaxing each constraint $\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c \geq 0$ to $\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c + c' \geq 0$, with c' large enough to ensure (12) holds. In particular, if $\mathbf{x} = L^{-1}\mathbf{x}' \in P \cap \mathbb{Z}^d$, i.e., $\langle \mathbf{a}, L^{-1}\mathbf{x}' \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c \geq 0$, then we must have $\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{q}' \in L'P$ for all $\mathbf{q}' \in L([0, 1]^d) \cap \mathbb{Z}^d$, i.e., $\langle \mathbf{a}, L^{-1}\mathbf{x}' \rangle + \langle \mathbf{a}, L^{-1}\mathbf{q}' \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c + c' \geq 0$ for all $L^{-1}\mathbf{q}' \in [0, 1]^d \cap L^{-1}\mathbb{Z}^d$. An appropriate choice for c' is

therefore

$$c' = \max_{\mathbf{q}' \in L([0, 1]^d) \cap \mathbb{Z}^d} -\langle \mathbf{a}, L^{-1}\mathbf{q}' \rangle. \quad (13)$$

If inflation is performed before expansion, then L is unknown and we need to make a further approximation of (13) as

$$c' = \max_{\mathbf{q} \in [0, 1]^d} -\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{q} \rangle = - \sum_{\{k | a_k < 0\}} a_k, \quad (14)$$

Note that here we cannot exploit the fact the the unit cell is half open since the coordinate values of \mathbf{q} may be arbitrarily close to 1.

EXAMPLE 6. Consider the parametric polytope P (9) from Example 2. We compute $c'_{(a)} = 3$, $c'_{(b)} = 1$ and $c'_{(c)} = 1$. For the orthogonal expansion (Example 4), we obtain the upper bound

$$\#P_{(s,t)} \leq \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{2147}{50}s + \frac{1243}{50}t + \frac{2873}{75},$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$, while for the general expansion (Example 5), we obtain the upper bound

$$\#P_{(s,t)} \leq \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{437}{10}s + \frac{253}{10}t + \frac{119}{3},$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$. For this example, the upper bound based on the orthogonal expansion is more accurate, with an average relative error of 5.3% compared to 6% for the the bound based on the general expansion.

Inflation can also be performed after expansion and then we can compute c' more accurately. In this case, we can exploit the half-open character of the unit cell. In particular, the constraints of the (integer) linear program (13) are $\mathbf{0} \leq L^{-1}\mathbf{q}' < \mathbf{1}$. After clearing the denominators, we can replace each strict upper bound $\langle \mathbf{l}, \mathbf{q}' \rangle < m$ by $\langle \mathbf{l}, \mathbf{q}' \rangle \leq m - 1$ (since the \mathbf{q}' are integer). We can then solve this problem over the rationals and still obtain relatively accurate results. Note that the disadvantage of performing inflation after expansion is that the vertices have to be recalculated after the inflation.

EXAMPLE 7. Take the expanded polytope P'' (11) from Example 5. The domain over which we need to compute the maximum (13) is $0 \leq \frac{1}{5}q_1 < 1 \wedge 0 \leq \frac{4}{30}q_1 + \frac{5}{30}q_2 < 1$. or $0 \leq q_1 \leq 4 \wedge 0 \leq 4q_1 + 5q_2 \leq 29$. To compute c' for constraint (a'), we need to compute $c' \leq \max_{\mathbf{q}} [q_2] = \lfloor 29/5 \rfloor = 5$, where we solved the maximum over all rational \mathbf{q} satisfying the constraints. Since we are actually interested in the maximum over all integer \mathbf{q} and the objective function has integer coefficients, we can safely round down the results. The constraint is then adjusted to $-j' + 4s - 8t + 3 \geq 0$. We similarly find $c'_{(b)} = 2$ and $c'_{(c)} = 4$.

For deflation, we similarly need to add a (now negative) constant, obtained by replacing max in (13) by min. The resulting parametric polytope may be empty for some or

even *all* values of the parameters for which the original polytope is not empty. We refer to [19] for a more detailed discussion. Note that the enumerator of a deflated polytope will always evaluate to nonnegative values, while a lower bound derived directly from a piecewise quasi-polynomial as in Section 5 may evaluate to negative values.

9. Experiments and Comparison

The approximation techniques presented in this paper have been implemented in version 0.23 of the `barvinok` library [29]. Our experiments were performed on a 1.3GHz Athlon using this library and a slightly modified version of `PolyLib` [13], version 5.22.3. The input polyhedra we considered in our experiments originate from the following applications:

- cc** Computation of the number of cache lines and the number of memory pages accessed by a reference in a given execution of a loop nest [10].
- rd** Computation of reuse distances [3] over cache lines.
- vol** Computation of the communication volume [4].
- ms** Computation of live elements for memory size estimation [8, 9].
- cm** Computation of the number of cache misses in a loop [5].

For more information on these inputs, we refer to [9, 30, 32] and [28, Chapter 5].

It is difficult to quantify the accuracy of a polynomial approximation P of a quasi-polynomial Q . The chambers on which the polynomials are defined are usually infinite and the relative error typically decreases as the parameter values increase. To have at least some indication of the relative accuracy of the different methods, we computed the average “relative error” over all values of the parameters in the range $[-100, 100]$ for which the parametric polytope (as a rational set) is non-empty. The relative error we compute is $|P(\mathbf{p}) - Q(\mathbf{p})|/Q(\mathbf{p})$ if $Q(\mathbf{p}) \neq 0$ and $|P(\mathbf{p}) - Q(\mathbf{p})|$ otherwise. Note that we always compare against the *exact* enumerator Q . For the under- and over-approximations we have also verified during our experiments that they are indeed always under- and over-approximations, respectively.

Table 1 shows the results. The first column lists the application, where `ex1` and `ex2` refer to the polytopes from Section 2 and Example 2. The cache line count test set is split into a set with polynomial exact enumerators (`cc'`) and a set with quasi-polynomial exact enumerators (`cc`). All polytopes with polynomial enumerators have been removed from the other test sets. Note that this *disfavors* our methods since the other methods are typically not exact even in case of polynomial exact enumerators. The second column specifies the number of polytopes in the test set. The remaining columns show the relative errors for the different methods. The `sums` column refers to the technique of rewriting a polyhedron as nested intervals and evaluating nested sums, variations of

which appear in [21, 23, 26, 27] (see Section 4). The details of our nested sums and volume implementations are explained in [29]. In contrast to the other examples, the `ms` and `cm` examples were evaluated over the first 1000 values of the parameters in the parameter domain of each example. These example sets are therefore separated from the other example sets in the table.

The table shows that the accuracy is highly dependent on the application. For approximation, the `drop`, `volume` and `scale` methods seem consistently more accurate than the `sum` method. For computation of safe bounds: although the `scale` method is relatively inaccurate for computing the under-approximation in the `cc` examples, the `drop` method is very inaccurate for computing both under- and over-approximation in the (much more numerous) `rd` and `ms` examples. As expected, the most accurate method is the in/deflation after expansion (method “A”). However, the relative improvement over other `scale` methods seems quite marginal. Except for the `cc'` test set, where the exact enumerator is a polynomial, the relative error of the `volume` is comparable to that of the `scale` methods. The nested sums technique gives results comparable to the over-approximating scaling methods. This is to be expected as in some cases it can be proven that this method does indeed yield an upper bound [27]. A notable exception here is again the `cc'` test set.

The top of Table 2 shows some computation time measurements. The computation of the other test sets was too fast for a meaningful comparison given the resolution of our timing measurements. As can be expected, the `drop` method takes slightly longer than the exact method, since it computes the exact solution first.

The bottom of Table 2 shows the average size of the enumerators. The sizes of the approximations are smaller than the sizes of the exact enumerator, sometimes dramatically (`cm`). The `cm` example suggests that nested sum method does not scale as well as the other methods. One possible explanation for that is that the use of nested intervals entails a significantly higher number of validity domains.

The size of the under-approximation is dramatically lower than expected (i.e., than the size of the over-approximation) in four tests: `rd`, `rd2`, `cm` and to a smaller degree `ms`. The reason for this is that these polyhedra are “thin” enough to become empty when deflated within some parameter domains (see [19]). Hence, their under-approximation is merely zero. These polyhedra are precisely the examples whose over-approximations have a shockingly high relative error (set in bold font in Table 1). They are “*difficult*” polyhedra, discussed in more detail in section 10. In these cases, the high relative over-approximation error is aggravated by the fact that the values of the enumerator are relatively small (over the sampling domain).

Table 1. Average relative error (%). Drop: method from Section 5; vol: volume; scale: method from Section 6; \perp : orthogonal expansion; B: in/deflation before expansion; A: in/deflation after expansion.

	# tests	approximation					under-approximation					over-approximation				
		sums	drop	vol	scale		drop	vol	scale			drop	vol	scale		
					\perp	B			A	\perp A	B			A	\perp A	
ex1	1	7.6	5.3	24	20	20	8.0	45	42	39	39	9.4	18	26	16	16
ex2	1	1.7	.24	1.8	1.3	1.7	1.1	6.3	6.0	5.3	5.8	1.2	5.1	6.0	4.3	4.5
cc	229	95	24	23	23	23	25	24	24	24	24	48	97	97	97	97
cc'	1333	293	0	80	0	0	0	82	81	2.3	2.3	0	2.3	82	2.3	2.3
rd	8765	145	102	74	75	75	29k	68	68	63	63	29k	333	391	179	314
rd2	2578	4.5k	513	306	426	424	20k	74	74	74	74	44k	10k	10k	7.2k	9.8k
vol	5	21	12	33	24	24	24	64	61	56	56	21	21	37	21	21
ms	19	252	5.3	37	32	36	85k	73	72	70	72	85k	275	286	266	264
cm	21	20k	633k	163	210	177	1.3G	63	63	63	63	1.3G	28M	28M	27M	27M

Table 2. Computation time and enumerator size. Columns as in Table 1.

	exact	approximation					under-approximation					over-approximation				
		sums	drop	vol	scale		drop	vol	scale			drop	vol	scale		
					\perp	B			A	\perp A	B			A	\perp A	
computation time (clock ticks, 0.01s)																
rd	3	< 1	3	< 1	< 1	< 1	3	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	3	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1
rd2	441	< 1	450	135	2	2	446	< 1	< 1	1	1	445	146	2	2	2
ms	4	2	3	1	2	1	4	< 1	< 1	< 1	< 1	4	1	1	2	2
cm	5.4k	56	5.5k	72	11	8	5.5k	< 1	< 1	4	2	5.5k	60	11	6	4
size of enumerator (32-bit words)																
ex1	489	246	148	130	148	148	290	149	149	148	148	290	149	149	149	149
ex2	360	704	101	101	101	101	295	101	101	101	101	295	101	101	101	101
cc	208	49	49	47	47	47	49	35	37	37	37	49	47	47	47	47
rd	299	101	101	96	104	104	79	10	10	16	15	100	104	104	110	110
rd2	510	149	87	100	98	98	61	8	8	9	9	85	100	100	100	100
vol	118	76	76	103	75	75	75	103	103	76	76	76	76	103	76	76
ms	972	436	206	220	244	244	206	38	38	52	38	206	240	240	244	252
cm	135k	4.4k	233	235	231	231	237	7	7	7	7	235	188	192	187	189

10. Room for Improvement

In this section, we show that the approximation techniques based on scaling do not yet take advantage of all available degrees of freedom. In particular, they can be improved by a slight shifting of the polyhedron's facets. Also, we characterize a class of polytopes that currently leads to safe bounds of poor quality, which we call *difficult*.

10.1 Shifting the Facets

Consider a rational parametric inequality, of the form:

$$\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c \geq 0,$$

where we assume that the g.c.d. of the coordinates of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} is 1 (replacing c by $\lfloor c/g \rfloor$, with g said g.c.d., if necessary). The set of integer points included by this inequality stays the same when changing this inequality to:

$$\langle \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{x} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{p} \rangle + c + \delta \geq 0 \quad 0 \leq \delta < 1. \quad (15)$$

Hence, any rational parametric polyhedron P , defined as the intersection of rational parametric inequalities, includes the exact same set of integer points as a potentially infinite family of polyhedra whose inequalities are derived from those of P as in (15). As a consequence, these polyhedra have the same enumerator as P . However, they do not in general have the same approximation. This is because the choice of δ in (15) affects the number of integer points in the expanded polyhedron.

EXAMPLE 8. Consider the following polyhedron:

$$P = \left\{ (i, j) \mid \begin{array}{l} 2i - 3j + 2s - 4t - 1 \geq 0 \\ -i + 4j + 6t - 3 \geq 0 \\ -i + 6s + 4t + 12 \geq 0 \end{array} \right\}.$$

Its enumerator is

$$\#P_{(s,t)} = \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{1007}{30}s + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{583}{30}t + C(s, t),$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$, where $C(s, t)$ is a periodic constant, and the scale approximation gives:

$$\#P_{(s,t)} \approx \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{931}{30}s + \frac{539}{30}t + 20,$$

if $19s + 11t + 23 \geq 0$. Polyhedron P' , obtained by adding $\frac{1}{2}$ to inequalities (a) and (c):

$$P = \left\{ (i, j) \mid \begin{array}{l} 4i - 6j + 4s - 8t - 1 \geq 0 \\ -i + 4j + 6t - 3 \geq 0 \\ -2i + 12s + 8t + 25 \geq 0 \end{array} \right\}$$

contains the same integer points and therefore has the same enumerator as P . However, its approximation is:

$$\#P'_{(s,t)} \approx \frac{361}{30}s^2 + \frac{209}{15}st + \frac{121}{30}t^2 + \frac{1007}{30}s + \frac{583}{30}t + \frac{117}{5}.$$

The approximation given by P' is better than the one obtained from P , as its absolute error is bounded by a constant (0.4) whereas the approximation derived from P has an absolute error of degree one.

10.2 Safe Approximations: Difficult Cases

As seen in Section 9, the inflation/deflation methods can fail to give a satisfyingly tight bound in the case when the degree of the d -dimensional polytope P is less than d , say $d - h$. In this case, knowing that the term of degree d is exact (exactly zero) does not guarantee good approximation properties.

If such a polytope has at least one parametric constraint, then the polytope must be bounded by pairs of parallel constraints at a constant distance such that the normals of these hyperplanes span an h -dimensional space. This case can be easily detected and the user can be warned that the safe bounds may be of poor quality.

In compiler problems, these polytopes typically appear in loops that have been strip-mined or come from *linearizations* of loop indices involved in integer parts or integer division remainder operations. For instance, $a \bmod b$ may be turned into the expression $(a - kb)$, with $0 \leq a - kb < b$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$.

These polytopes obviously require special treatment. In particular cases when the distance between the parallel constraints is small enough, the polytope can be decomposed into a fixed number of $(d - h)$ -dimensional non-difficult polytopes. Otherwise, we can always find a unimodular transformation (which preserves the enumerator) that puts the parallel pairs of constraints along unit vectors. Preliminary experiments show that by using this transformation, along with inflation after orthogonal expansion, the relative error of the rd2 test set is reduced by a factor of four. We are currently working on more methods based on treating the parallel pairs of constraints in a special way. They will be presented in the future.

11. Conclusion and Future Work

We have proposed several methods for computing polynomial functions that reliably approximate the enumerator of a

polyhedron. The *drop* method is based on modifying the exact enumerator and the *scale* method on expanding the polyhedron. An important advantage of these methods compared to other approximation methods is that they give the *exact* solution if this exact solution can be represented by a polynomial. Both methods also allow for the computation of safe upper and lower bounds of the enumerator of a polyhedron, using additional techniques presented in this paper.

We have seen that the *scale* approximation method seems to perform better than other existing methods. The rational volume of the polyhedron gives results of similar quality when the exact enumerator is not already non-periodic (or has a small period). It is equivalent to taking the *scale* approximation with an expansion matrix of infinite determinant. The inflation/deflation methods for computing bounds can therefore be used in combination with either the *scale* method or the rational volume computation. Our experiments indicate that the three methods are quite accurate, except in some “*difficult*” cases where the bound calculation is dramatically off. There are ways to deal with these, but they are not treated in detail in this paper. Preliminary experiments suggest that further polyhedral transformations could be used to improve the accuracy of approximations and bounds, even for non-*difficult* polyhedra.

In a continuing effort to make the most powerful tools of the polyhedral model more usable and used, all the methods presented in this paper were implemented in the freely available *barvinok* library, and some of them in Reservoir Lab’s Java polyhedral library *jolylib*.

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